

DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION, THEIR TYPES AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THEIR USE (AS AN EXAMPLE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE)

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Information technologies have firmly entered our lives and changed the habitual way of life of people of the last century - people use them every day for learning, at work or at home. Computer literacy and information culture are necessary conditions for employment and a successful career. The trend of increasing the multifunctionality of things that surround a person is rapidly developing. For example, mobile phones have ceased to function only as a means of communication; their functionality has expanded almost to the level of a computer.

Foreign language learning has also recently been influenced by digital technologies. In the process of teaching a foreign language, information technologies and digital educational resources are increasingly used, which make it possible to diversify the types of activities in the classroom.

Presentation of the main material of the article. Information technologies in teaching foreign languages act as technical equipment for the educational process in the form of electronic devices and resources. Polzikova E.V. divides information technologies into training, development, and educational. Educational information technologies help in solving educational problems when used systematically.

Developmental information technologies are aimed at enhancing the cognitive activity of students. Educational information technologies make it possible to expand the cognitive abilities of students in order to satisfy their intellectual needs. The use of authentic audio and video materials in the process of teaching a foreign language has become the subject of research by many scientists. C. Herron and I. Seay argue that the use of authentic audio and video materials improves listening comprehension at all levels of learning, without having a negative impact on grammar, vocabulary and oral language skills [1].

The results of a study conducted by J.M. Chung [2], in which authentic video materials were used in a Taiwan EFL college in a combined approach of

pre-teaching vocabulary and topic study, confirmed that authentic video materials have a positive effect on listening learning. A study by T. Asako argues that TED Talks influence the listening skills of college students in Japan and examines strategies for adapting classes for students with low proficiency. According to the analysis of the data obtained, students show an improvement in listening comprehension, an increase in the level of motivation and the ability to understand various English accents.

H. Kim's study examined the effect of authentic video resources on improving listening comprehension in the educational process among Korean university students. Research has revealed a significant improvement in listening comprehension in groups with intermediate and advanced levels of foreign language proficiency after using video materials [2].

Among the educational tasks that are solved through the use of information technologies in the learning process, the following can be identified: maintaining students' motivation for discipline through the systematic use of electronic resources in the process of learning a foreign language, increasing the level of professional competence of the teacher, improving the educational process as a whole, expanding opportunities for organizing educational activities of students [3].

From the perspective of a targeted approach to teaching, digital educational resources pursue the following pedagogical goals:

- fulfillment of the social order of society: the use of ICT promotes the development of an information literate individual, regardless of specialization;
- improvement of all levels of the educational process through the use of ICT involves the implementation of the educational process at a high level, the activation of students' cognitive activity, as well as the formation of an information culture for students;
- adaptation of all participants in the educational process to life in the conditions of information technology, which is expressed by the formation of the necessary skills and abilities for orientation in global information flows.

Thus, thanks to the active use of digital educational resources in the modern educational process, there is a change in the content, methods and forms of teaching.

Today, a foreign language is in demand from the point of view of expanding communication opportunities with the world community. Modern digital educational resources are used by many teachers in their professional

activities, because... they are a promising driver for increasing the effectiveness of English language teaching.

Among the most popular digital educational resources that can be used in the process of learning a foreign language:

✓ *Lingualeo.com* is a platform for learning vocabulary, practicing reading skills, listening to authentic audio recordings, videos with subtitles in a foreign language.

✓ *Duolingo.com* is a resource for developing speaking skills in a playful way.

✓ *Rong-chang.com* is a universal course in which training is carried out on the principle of testing in the sections of grammar, vocabulary, and spelling.

✓ *Learn It* - a resource that allows you to study a foreign language in a group or individually, as well as in three-month marathons.

✓ *BistroEnglish.com* is an original joint project, developed with the active participation of native linguists, offering to learn a foreign language through a set of audio and video lessons, educational and game interactive format, and a variety of thematic lessons.

Thus, among the advantages of using digital educational resources in the process of learning a foreign language, the following can be highlighted: strengthening positive motivation for learning, enhancing the cognitive activity of students; conducting classes at a high aesthetic and emotional level; attracting a large volume of didactic material; ensuring a high degree of differentiation and individualization of training; expanding the possibility of independent activity; developing skills in design and research activities; providing access to various reference systems, electronic libraries, and other information resources.

The educational process using digital educational resources is aimed at developing logical and critical thinking, imagination, and independence of students. Successful development of cognitive activity and independence of students is possible when the educational process is organized as intensive intellectual activity of each student, taking into account his characteristics and capabilities using various modern means.

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